

Design and Implementation of Genetic Algorithms in Actual Quantum Devices: The Annealing Paradigm on DWAVE

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In this article we encompass the first comprehensive work in the process of translating modern optimization algorithms from classic computers to quantum computers. We will start with an evolutionary algorithm (EA), a wide class of optimization techniques having deep impact in present research and industry. We will go, step by step, through all the operations in a canonical EA, and translate them into a program amenable for running both, on a simulator and on an actual quantum device (the popular DWAVE). Here, we are not building an EA with quantum inspired operations running on a classic computer, much on the contrary, we run EAs on a real quantum computer. We have tried to make the article as much self-contained as possible, so that novel and interested researchers can reproduce our methodology and learn how to program EAs on a quantum computer. In our way from classic to quantum, we include the needed bases to understand the background concepts, and will end with a real evaluation of the results of the quantum EA, so that we follow the whole chain from the abstract concept to the final evaluation on a problem, considering the usual best practices in the EA field.

I. INTRODUCTION

Optimization is maybe one of the most pervasive activities in human history. From informal optimization of our time, our work, and our money, to the highly scientific activities found in global optimization and complex system optimization that solve problems in medicine, economy, smart cities, industry 4.0, and so many other fields of application. Optimization (and consequently search and learning) are today paramount in most research and innovation disciplines, and thus the literature is full of procedures and results [1–3].

Indeed, optimization is an activity found in computer science, mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology and so many other fields, [4–6] and that is the reason for the high impact of any new procedure that solves problems in a faster or more accurate way compared to the state of the art. Indeed, there are many ways in which problems are solved, and there is a plethora of exact, approximate, hybrid techniques to do so. Metaheuristics [7–9], for example, are well-known to be able of finding global optima in problems of high dimensionality, with many non-linear restrictions, and where the goal function is non-continuous, non-derivable or even non-known at all (then simulations are used).

In this context, many lines of research are trying to level up the present efficiency, accuracy, and usability of search, optimization and learning algorithms [1]. Some of them try to create techniques by relying in theoretical advances, others build new software toolboxes, other are merging optimization tools to machine learning... and many others are trying to translate existing concepts to new hardware platforms. Here, we can mention using manycore computers, FPGAs, or even new algorithms for GPUs [10, 11]. In general, these new platforms require to re-build the software, the technique and the very idea of how solutions are sought. And here we are that we go in a somewhat similar way in proposing to run optimization techniques on quantum computers, with the consequent

need to de-construct and re-construct them. Of course, there are some optimization algorithms already translated to the quantum field [12–15], but we here face the methodology and tricks to focus in the algorithm, so that it becomes a well-known procedure and the community of research quickly enter the realm of quantum computing in a smooth manner.

Quantum computing is a growing field based in the fact that we should forget on traditional Turing machines and Von Neumann programs. The way in which we program with C, Java and Python will suffer a big change if we want to program quantum computers. Beyond usual expectations when the platform for computing changes, here even languages are no longer useful and we should concentrate e.g. in developing quantum circuits [16] or quantum adiabatic computation [17] procedures. Quantum programming is a new exercise, and quantum computers are so full of restrictions and advances that we need a fresh start.

With the present paper, we want to start a series of articles that will delve with the translation of concepts from classic programming to quantum programming, but not in general, but in particular for search, optimization and learning. Our first paper is this one, where we will take a canonical evolutionary algorithm (EA) [18, 19], a well-known type of metaheuristic, and explain how to design and implement it in a real quantum device. A main decision here is between IBM Q experience and DWAVE, and we go for this second option for reasons we will explain later.

Our contributions here are many: (a) we build a complete quantum optimization metaheuristic, (b) we are not “quantum inspired” but we run a successful solver in a real quantum device, (c) we offer a methodological and pedagogical description on how to do this for non-specialists, (d) we discuss implementation options to encourage further research, and (e) we evaluate the technique either numerically and in real time including the best practices in the EA field.

The main research questions that we will try to answer are those:

RQ1 How can we adapt a canonical EA from classic computers to a quantum annealing model for a real device?

RQ2 What are the strong and weak sides of a quantum EA and the limits of current devices for running them?

We want to reinforce the idea that we are not making here anything similar to the existing *quantum inspired* algorithms, but a complete quantum algorithm for optimization that is not linked directly to the annealing or Q circuits philosophy: we follow the structure of the search in an EA and then see what is the best/easiest ways of implementing it on a quantum computing.

This paper is structured in the following sections. In the next sections we explain our approach, and the bases for our methodology to allow a universal way of translating EAs to quantum devices. In Section II we first revisit a canonical EA(1+1) algorithm and explain its component operations. In Section III we introduce the concept of *quantum annealing* and describe the Ising computational model that represents a well-known annealing procedure. Section IV is devoted to transform the EA operations in an amenable way to be run as an Ising model. In Section V we complete the algorithm, developing a fitness function implementation for an illustrative optimization problem. In Section VI we move to the final step and we describe how to run the algorithm on an actual device, considering the limitations that affect the algorithm execution capabilities. Finally, in Section VII we include a short summary, a survey of main conclusions, and a discussion on potential future works (benefits and open challenges).

II. PHASE I: ALGORITHM MODEL FOR THE CANONICAL EA(1+1)

This section gives an introduction to the canonical EA(1+1) algorithm and the algorithm model that will ease its translation to a quantum EA.

A. Canonical EA(1+1)

A canonical EA(1+1) is a basic metaheuristic optimization algorithm. EAs use a set of encoded problem solutions plus a set of operators to modify them, guided by the quality (fitness) of these solutions. EAs can solve continuous, discrete, mixed and symbol-oriented problems, but we will focus here on fitness functions evaluated over binary representations. Thus, we consider problems with fixed size solutions represented as n bit strings. Indeed, any problem represented in binary strings can then be solved by the quantum EA that we are developing here.

We introduce first the solution space $\mathcal{S} = \{-1, +1\}^n$ of binary sequences of length n . Even if the standard binary notation is $\{0, 1\}$ we are using $\{-1, +1\}$ because the quantum implementation through an Ising annealing model (the one used in this paper) uses such representation for binary values. For an element of the solution space $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{S}$ we use the notation $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. The problem is defined by a fitness function $f : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ assigning a real number to each of the solutions. We assume that the goal is to minimize the fitness function, *i.e.* to find $\arg \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{S}} f(\mathbf{x})$.

The general idea is to manage one individual and improve it from generation to generation by applying only one evolutionary operator – mutation. As the population consists of one individual we will denote it as $\mathbf{x}^{(t)} \in \mathcal{S}$. At each generation, individual $\mathbf{x}^{(t)} \in \mathcal{S}$ is modified by mutation to yield $\mathbf{x}'^{(t)}$. The mutation operator considered in this work is probabilistic bit-flip operation. Each bit of the solution is flipped with probability P_m . In short, we have one tentative solution, and we perturb it by mutation, and we keep the new one if its fitness is equal or better than the existing one. We repeat this procedure T times and return the last solution.

The algorithm can be described as follows.

1. Sample n bits from a uniform binary distribution to compute $\mathbf{x}^{(1)}$ (EA operation I: the Initial Sampling Operator).
2. For $t = 1, \dots, T$ repeat.
 - (a) Perform mutation to individual $\mathbf{x}^{(t)}$, generating $\mathbf{x}'^{(t)}$, by performing bit flip operation at each position independently with probability P_m (EA operation II: the Mutation Operator).
 - (b) Evaluate and compare the individuals' fitness function values $f(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})$ and $f(\mathbf{x}'^{(t)})$ (EA operation III: the Comparison Operator).
 - (c) Select individual for next generation replacing the individual with the mutated one, assigning $\mathbf{x}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{x}'^{(t)}$, if $f(\mathbf{x}'^{(t)}) \leq f(\mathbf{x}^{(t)})$ and keeping the previous one, by assigning $\mathbf{x}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{x}^{(t)}$, otherwise (EA operation IV: the Replacement Operator).
3. return $\mathbf{x}^{(T+1)}$.

B. Slightly Modifying the Standard EA Description to Fit Quantum Programming

We aim at establishing an *algorithm model* for EA(1+1) – a description of both canonical and quantum EA, so that on seeing the same input, our quantum algorithm will return the same output. This is schematically presented in Fig. 1. Thus, we will consider the same variables as in the previous sections and translate each of the EA operations into a set of relations between

the variables. This is needed because the quantum EA will be expressed in terms of variables and their relationships. In the next sections we design a procedure based on quantum annealing that use the described variables and implement the introduced relationships.

FIG. 1. The algorithm model for both the canonical EA(1+1) and the quantum EA developed in this work. Two algorithms correspond to the same algorithm model if, for a given input, the output distribution is the same. Here the input f is a fitness function, and $\mathbf{x}^{(T+1)}$ is the expected output.

A canonical EA is a non-deterministic algorithm, and so will be the quantum EA. Thus, to describe the model of the algorithm we need to specify the mapping from the input to the output probability distribution. In our case the output probability distribution can be described as a collection of marginal probability distributions and the statistical dependencies between output variables. For this we need to specify what we consider to be the output of the algorithms, what statistical dependencies correspond to the canonical EA Operators and how the statistical dependencies relate to the input.

We start by taking the canonical EA model of the previous section and then add some new variables (called algorithm model variables) that will adapt the canonical standard EA description to the one needed for a quantum EA. The variables previously used to describe the canonical EA were

- population individuals $\mathbf{x}^{(t)} \in \mathcal{S}$, for $t = 1, \dots, T$,
- individuals after mutation $\mathbf{x}'^{(t)} \in \mathcal{S}$, for $t = 1, \dots, T$

and we additionally introduce new variables in order to be able to translate EA operations into relationships. Namely,

- for the Mutation Operator: mutation control variables $m_i^{(t)} \in \{-1, 1\}$, variables $e_i^{(t)}$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$, and auxiliary variables $\delta_{i,j}^{(t)}$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$, $t = 1, \dots, T$, and $j = 1, \dots, k$

for some k we choose depending on P_m (we use $k = -\log_2(P_m)$ or $k = 1/P_m$),

- for the Comparison Operator: comparison variables $c^{(t)} \in \{-1, 1\}$, for $t = 1, \dots, T$,
- for the Replacement Operator: replacement equality control variables $s_i^{(t)} \in \{-1, 1\}$, and $s_i'^{(t)}$, for $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$.

As it will be explained in detail later in Sec. IV A, due to the use of the uniform binary distribution, there is no reason for creating any new variables in the case of the Initial Sampling Operator.

The output distribution can be described with statistical dependencies corresponding to the EA operations and the input fitness function. We introduce the statistical dependencies for each of the EA operations separately. First, for the Initial Sampling Operator we introduce relation

$$(I) x_i^{(1)} = 1 \text{ with probability } 1/2, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n.$$

For the Mutation Operator we introduce two relations

$$(M1) \text{ values of variables } m_i^{(t)} \text{ should be equal to } 1 \text{ with probability } P_m, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n, t = 1, \dots, T,$$

$$(M2) x_i^{(t)} = -x_i'^{(t)} \text{ iff } m_i^{(t)} = 1, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, n, t = 1, \dots, T.$$

We consider evaluation jointly with the comparison operation as a single relation

$$(E) c^{(t)} = 1 \text{ iff } f(\mathbf{x}'^{(t)}) \leq f(\mathbf{x}^{(t)}), \text{ for } t = 1, \dots, T.$$

For the Replacement Operation we introduce two relations:

$$(R1) \mathbf{x}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{x}^{(t)} \text{ if } c^{(t)} = -1, \text{ for } t = 1, \dots, T,$$

$$(R2) \mathbf{x}^{(t+1)} = \mathbf{x}'^{(t)} \text{ if } c^{(t)} = +1, \text{ for } t = 1, \dots, T.$$

The output of the algorithm is $\mathbf{x}^{(T+1)}$. As some of the variables are not explicitly included in the above relations, we explain their role later in Section IV.

We will develop quantum EA as a procedure that harness quantum annealing to find a set of variables that satisfy all of the introduced relationships.

III. QUANTUM EA

In this section we present the overall architecture of the introduced quantum EA and the foundations necessary for its development. We give a basic introduction to quantum annealing (QA), and the existing devices that implement it.

What we here call *quantum EA* is a completely new algorithm that gives the same results as the canonical EA, but designed, implemented and run completely in a quantum computer. The idea is illustrated in Fig. 1. We

use the concept of an *algorithm model*, a description of the algorithm behavior concerning which output distribution should we expect for a given input.

The quantum EA is an algorithm based on quantum annealing, which can be seen as an *atomic procedure*: giving an energy function F , a state of low energy (*ground state*)

$$\mathbf{s}^* \in \{-1, 1\}^N : F(\mathbf{s}^*) = \min_{\mathbf{s} \in \{-1, 1\}^N} F(\mathbf{s}), \quad (1)$$

is returned. The energy function is usually called the Hamiltonian function of the system. The procedure is illustrated in Fig. 2. In general, to perform an annealing procedure one needs to specify what is the energy function F .

FIG. 2. The quantum annealing as an atomic procedure, which for given energy function F returns a ground state \mathbf{s}^* . In particular, we consider energy functions that can be expressed as in Eq. (2).

The algorithm that we develop in this work is aimed at solving optimization problems given by pseudo-boolean functions. The quantum EA will consist of three main steps. In Step 1, we perform *translation*: the fitness function f given as input and the relations corresponding to all of the operators of canonical EA of all of the generations jointly are zipped into one single energy function F for the quantum EA. In Step 2, a quantum annealing procedure is run to obtain a ground state \mathbf{s}^* . Finally, in Step 3 we perform *reverse translation* the ground state to \mathbf{s}^* get the solution $\mathbf{x}^{(T+1)}$ that minimizes the input

fitness function f . Thus, we start with the input fitness function f and obtain $\mathbf{x}^{(T+1)}$ via

- Step 1 (Direct_translation): $f \mapsto F$,
- Step 2 (Annealing): $F \mapsto \mathbf{s}^*$,
- Step 3 (Reverse_translation): $\mathbf{s}^* \mapsto \mathbf{x}^{(T+1)}$.

The idea is presented in Fig. 3. Step 2. and Step 3. are quite straightforward once an energy function has been created. Thus, our main goal is to obtain a proper translation scheme that returns an energy function encapsulating both variables and their relationships as described in Section II B, from initialization to returning the final solution. This goal requires several steps, presented in Fig. 4.

FIG. 3. The quantum EA overview as described in Section III. For given input fitness function f the solution $\mathbf{x}^{(T+1)}$ is obtained via translation, quantum annealing and reverse translation.

The first phase has already been done in Sec. II B where we explicitly translated the canonical EA into a set of relationships between variables, obtaining what we called the algorithm model.

The goal of Phase II is to develop a direct/reverse translation procedure for the algorithm model established in Phase I. We want to obtain a single energy function that contains all of the relationships developed in section II B.

FIG. 4. The procedure of passing from the canonical EA to running the quantum EA on an actual device. The procedure is divided into four phases, as presented in this paper.

We proceed with the relationships corresponding to the EA operations separately, and then combine them to obtain a single translation procedure. The construction is schematically illustrated in Fig. 5.

Next, in Phase III, we develop an example. We consider the ONEMAX optimization problem and describe how to include the corresponding fitness function into an energy function resulting from the direct translation procedure developed in Phase II. With the corresponding reverse translation procedure we obtain a complete quantum EA.

In the final Phase IV, we use the actual device to run the algorithm. For this purpose we develop an *execution routine* for the quantum EA. The need for this additional procedure level comes from the limits of the available devices. The procedure will consist of several steps that split the energy function obtained through direct translation into parts that are run separately on the device, and then joining the partial results for the final result. In particular, we separate the universal part of the algorithm translation from the problem-related part, which depends on the fitness function.

In the remaining part of this section we briefly introduce quantum annealing and the quantum devices we use.

A. Quantum Annealing

Performing computation with quantum systems is so fundamentally different from classical-mechanical computation that we need completely new models to describe

the computation process, *i.e.* quantum computational models, such as *quantum circuits* and *quantum annealing*. Among existing models these two are the most significant ones when it comes to commercially available quantum devices. Both are *universal models*: they can be used to express any physically feasible computation. This also makes them theoretically equivalent: anything described within one of them can be translated to the other one. In this work we are concerned only with quantum annealing.

The goal of the quantum annealing process is to obtain a specific quantum system with a given energy function. This function has to be described within the model of the quantum system that we use. The design of the device that we use in this work requires an Ising model description.

A system within Ising model is described by a *size* and an *energy function*. Given size N , the set of states of the system is always the same – a collection of N sites (variables) s_i , $i = 1, \dots, N$ that can be assigned one of two values: 1 or -1 , *i.e.* $s_i \in \{-1, 1\}$. Anytime we call a variable being **true** we mean it has value $+1$, and -1 otherwise.

The energy function assigns a real number to the states. For each pair i, j of sites there can be an *interaction* introduced – change of energy depending of whether the sites s_i, s_j are assigned equal or opposite values. Each interaction is represented by a real number $J_{i,j} \in \mathbb{R}$, governing the magnitude of the energy change, $-J_{i,j}$ versus $J_{i,j}$.

FIG. 5. Quantum EA. The building block functions are described in Table I.

Additionally, each site i is assigned an energy value $h_i \in \mathbb{R}$, independent from other sites. As a result, the energy of a configuration $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_N)$ is given by a function consisting of two parts

$$F(\mathbf{s}) = - \sum_i h_i s_i - \sum_{i < j} J_{i,j} s_i s_j \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (2)$$

Let us note that, when designing the energy function for our algorithm, we will not define h_i and $J_{i,j}$ explicitly. We will be introducing formulas in the same form as in eq. (2) from which it is straightforward to obtain h_i and $J_{i,j}$ elements.

B. Hardware: Quantum Devices and Their Current Limits

Although we focus on quantum annealing approach, it is not the only way of using quantum devices to solve optimization problems described within an Ising model. **Another option is to use devices implementing quantum gate model. In particular, one can use a Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) [20, 21].** We decided not to pursue this way in this study due to very limited size of currently available devices. Another option is to use a digital circuit design inspired by quantum phenomena, a path followed by Fujitsu with a Digital Annealer [22, 23]. A comprehensive list of undergoing quantum computing hardware development projects can be found *e.g.* at [24].

In this work we aim at running the algorithm on the quantum annealing device provided by D-Wave Systems [25]. This choice is justified by the long standing time of D-Wave in the quantum computing field, as well as for its larger set of software tools available for it in comparison to other quantum devices.

Currently available devices are capable of providing approximate ground states as introduced in the previous section. However, there are some restrictions on the problem instances that can be solved. The most fundamental restriction is on the size of the quantum system. Current devices work with quantum system with 2048 sites, which allows to consider energy functions with at most that many variables. Another restriction is usually referred to as *connectivity restriction*. Using the introduced formalism, the interactions between sites defined by parameters $J_{i,j}$ cannot be all non-zero. The set of allowed interactions (parameters $J_{i,j}$ that can be non-zero) is described by *chimera graph* [26]. This architecture has been designed to allow complete graph embedding. However, the size of the embedded complete graph grows as a square root of the chimera graph, and is equal to 64 for a chimera graph of size 2048.

Although we can see an annealing device as a black box as presented in Fig. 2, because it is answering to a simple *device call*, we will consider a more detailed picture.

That is because in practice the device has some parameters that need to be set, and returns an output that need to be processed. Namely, we specify the *annealing time* and the number of *annealing repetitions*. As a result we obtain a collection of states (one for each repetition) with their energy values instead of just one state.

The parameters obviously affect the behavior of the device. In particular, it is important to know that a quantum device is never perfect as of today's technologies. It does not return the ground state every time that the annealing is run. The parameters give us two ways to tackle this imperfection. First, the longer the annealing time, the higher the probability of returning a ground state. Second, with higher number of repetitions it becomes more likely that at least one of the returned states is a ground state.

Moreover, due to our energy function design that we will present in this paper, in our experiments we will always know what is the minimal energy (which is not always the case). Thus, as we get the list of returned states, we will be able of identifying the ones that are optimal (*i.e.* a ground state). It may happen that none of the returned states is a ground state. We consider such a case an error of the annealing procedure, and repeat the whole device call.

Let us also comment on how the selection of the annealing time and the number of repetitions affect the total device call time. The total device call time observed by the user consists of a communication overhead t_{comm} and the actual QPU computation time t_{QPU} :

$$t_q = t_{comm} + t_{QPU} \quad (3)$$

By communication overhead we mean everything required to get the input from the local workstation to the remote quantum device, and get the output back. All of the operations happen outside of the quantum device. Thus, we focus on t_{QPU} as the one that express for how long do we need to have exclusive access to the key resource: the quantum annealer. In this sense the efficiency of the quantum annealing based algorithm can be measured by t_{QPU} .

This time is again split into initialization phase t_{init} and R repetitions time

$$t_{QPU} = t_{init} + R \cdot (t_{anneal} + t_d), \quad (4)$$

where t_{init} depends mainly on the energy function, whereas each repetition consists of the annealing time t_{anneal} and a constant delay between repetitions t_d . **Thus, increasing either the number of repetitions R or the annealing time t_{anneal} increases the probability of obtaining the ground state, but at a cost of greater t_{QPU} . Choosing the optimal values for minimal expected QPU computation time to reach a ground state is a nontrivial task.** We will report the exact times obtained during the experiments in the results section.

IV. PHASE II: DIRECT TRANSLATION

In this section we move directly to the crucial step of the quantum EA, namely Step 1 – the direct translation. Operations of the EA are actual *relations* between variables included in the minimized energy function F . We simply want to obtain a function $F(s)$ that reaches its minimal value if and only if all of the output distribution constraints of EA(1+1) algorithm model are satisfied.

We proceed across three levels of detail. We begin with describing the translation overview and how the energy function is designed. Then, at the second level, we describe single EA operations, using some energy function building blocks (sections IV A-IV D). Finally, as a third level, we introduce a detailed description of these building blocks, that show explicitly the statistical relations between variables that define the model (section IV E). The goal is to develop a single energy function as presented in Eq. (2) that represents the fitness function and the algorithm. This function will be represented as a sum of energy functions, which we call *energy function components* $F_I, F_M, F_E, F_R : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, each corresponding to single EA operation

$$F(\mathbf{s}) = F_I(\mathbf{s}) + F_M(\mathbf{s}) + F_E(\mathbf{s}) + F_R(\mathbf{s}). \quad (5)$$

Each component is a quadratic function on its own, meaning that

$$F_\Phi(\mathbf{s}) = - \sum_i h_i^\Phi s_i - \sum_{i < j} J_{i,j}^\Phi s_i s_j, \quad (6)$$

where $\Phi \in \{I, M, E, R\}$. The schematic structure is presented in Fig. 6. The design of the components makes it possible to find a state that is a minimal energy state with respect to each of the components. Thus, a minimal energy state with respect to the sum of them all will be such a state. These components are not designed to be used for annealing on their own. Additionally, each of the energy function components is described with use of *energy function building blocks* – functions that introduce single dependence between given variables. The functions are also presented in Table I with the the relationships between input variables that they introduce.

From now on we will assume that there is a fixed mapping between the quantum annealing variables $s = (s_1 \dots, s_N)$ and the algorithm model variables as introduced in Section II B. Thus, we will consider the energy function F and the energy components F_I, F_E, F_M, F_R as functions acting on all these variables.

A. EA Operations I: the Initial Sampling Operator

The first EA operation is initialization, which corresponds to function F_I . In general the function affects only the first generation, and for consistency we will write it as

$$F_I(x_1^{(1)}, \dots, x_n^{(1)}) = \sum_i f_I(x_i^{(1)}) \quad (7)$$

FIG. 6. Quantum EA mostly consists of encoding the fitness function into an energy function F . We develop the energy function as a sum of four components, $F = F_I + F_M + F_E + F_S$, each corresponding to an EA operation.

We propose a trivial function being $f_I = 0$. The Ising model is based on binary values and its underlying premise is that all of the states with the same energy are returned with equal probability. In consequence, if the energy is the same for each input state, the resulting marginal probability distribution corresponding to each bit should be uniform.

B. EA Operations II: the Mutation Operator

In this section we define the energy function component F_M , the one corresponding to the mutation operation. We will describe the component with function f_M considering only one generation t and only one solution variable i at the time, using a form

$$F_M(\{\mathbf{m}^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{x}^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{x}'^{(t)}\}_t, \{\delta^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{e}^{(t)}\}_t) = \sum_{t,i} f_M(m_i^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}, \delta_i^{(t)}, e_i^{(t)}). \quad (8)$$

Here we write the dependence on the algorithm model variables, omitting auxiliary variables presented in Fig. 6. To reflect the statistical dependencies resulting from the mutation operation with the Ising model we need to design an energy function component with all minimal energy states satisfying the dependencies (M1-2) in section II B.

We introduce two types of auxiliary variables, one for point (M1) and the second one to introduce (M2). Namely, we introduce variables $\{\delta_{i,j}^{(t)}\}, j = 1, \dots, k$, for some k . These will allow us to generate probability distribution with operations on auxiliary variables. By in-

FIG. 7. Illustration of the building blocks of the energy function component for the mutation operation. The component introduces dependence between main variables, $m_i^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}$ and auxiliary variables $e_i^{(t)}, \delta_{i,j}^{(t)}$. The component is a sum of three blocks that depend on the corresponding variables as illustrated.

roducing variables $e_i^{(t)}$, which will be **true** iff $x_i^{(t)} = x_i'^{(t)}$ we translate (M2). The construction is sketched in Fig. 7.

We design mutation energy function component f_M as a sum of three building blocks

$$f_M(m_i^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}, \delta_{i,j}^{(t)}, e_i^{(t)}) = \quad (9)$$

$$\text{assert_AND}(m_i^{(t)}, \{\delta_{i,j}^{(t)}\}_j) +$$

$$\text{assert_opposite}(e_i^{(t)}, m_i^{(t)}) + \quad (10)$$

$$\text{check_equality}(e_i^{(t)}, (x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)})),$$

The building block functions are as introduced in Table I.

Function	Effect
$\text{assert_opposite}(a, b)$	$a = -b$
$\text{assert_if_then_else}(c, a, b)$	$c = 1 \implies a = 1$ and $c = -1 \implies b = 1$
$\text{assert_AND}(a, \{b_j\}_j)$	$a = 1 \iff b_1 = 1 \wedge b_2 = 1 \wedge \dots$
$\text{check_equality}(e, (a, b))$	$a = b \iff e = 1$
$\text{compare}_f(c, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$	$c = 1 \iff f(\mathbf{y}) \leq f(\mathbf{x})$

TABLE I. Building block functions. The effect clauses are true for all ground states.

In this work we only consider mutation control variables $m_i^{(t)}$ that should be **true** with probability $P_m = 2^{-k}$ for any non-negative integer k . We obtain such probability by using k bits $\delta_{i,j}^{(t)}$, each being 1 with probability 2^{-1} and requiring that $m_i^{(t)} = \text{AND}(\delta_{i,1}^{(t)}, \dots, \delta_{i,k}^{(t)})$. This way the resulting value of $m_i^{(t)}$ is 1 (**true**) only if all of the bits are 1, what should happen with probability 2^{-k} .

C. EA Operations III: the Comparison Operator

We translate the effect of the evaluation operator with energy function component F_E . As stated in Section II B we consider the Evaluation Operator jointly with the comparison part of the Replacement Operator. For consistency, we define the component as a sum of functions f_E , which considers each of the generations separately

$$F_E(\{c^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{x}^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{x}'^{(t)}\}_t) = \sum_t f_E(c^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}'^{(t)}). \quad (11)$$

At this level of detail we only represent the function using one of the building blocks

$$f_E(c^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}'^{(t)}) = \text{compare}_f(c^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}'^{(t)}). \quad (12)$$

All of the building block functions are explained in detail in Section IV E.

D. EA Operations IV: the Replacement Operator

We proceed with the replacement energy function component F_R similarly to the mutation component – with function f_R considering only one generation t and only one solution variable i at the time, using a similar definition, namely

$$F_R(\{c^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{x}^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{x}'^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{s}^{(t)}\}_t, \{\mathbf{s}'^{(t)}\}_t) = \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{t,i} f_R(c^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}, x_i^{(t+1)}, s_i^{(t)}, s_i'^{(t)}).$$

Building an energy function component that corresponds to the replacement operator requires considering two conditions (R1-2 in section II B). Thus, we want to obtain a function F_R , such that the two conditions are satisfied among all of the minimal energy states. A schematic illustration can be seen in Fig. 8.

The comparison operation has been considered jointly with the evaluation operation. Thus, substitution operation is dependent on the value of the comparison variable $c^{(t)}$.

We introduce two types of auxiliary variables $s_i^{(t)}$ and $s_i'^{(t)}$. We also introduce additional dependencies, namely we want $s_i^{(t)}$ to be **true** iff $\mathbf{x}^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}^{(t+1)}$ and $s_i'^{(t)}$ to be **true** iff $\mathbf{x}'^{(t)} = \mathbf{x}'^{(t+1)}$.

Building the energy function component in the introduced way requires defining the function as a sum of three building blocks

$$f_R(c^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}, x_i^{(t+1)}, s_i^{(t)}, s_i'^{(t)}) = \quad (14)$$

$$\text{check_equality}(s_i^{(t)}, (x_i^{(t)}, x_i^{(t+1)})) +$$

$$\text{check_equality}(s_i'^{(t)}, (x_i'^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t+1)})) +$$

$$\text{assert_if_then_else}(c^{(t)}, s_i'^{(t)}, s_i^{(t)}),$$

FIG. 8. Illustration of the building blocks of the energy function component for the replacement operation. The component introduces dependence between main variables, $c^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}, x_i^{(t+1)}$ and auxiliary variables $s_i^{(t)}, s_i'^{(t)}$. The component is a sum of three building blocks that depend on the corresponding variables as illustrated.

where the first two blocks are designed to satisfy the conditions related to the auxiliary variables for all minimal energy states. Due to the definition of the `assert_if_then_else` building block, the individual in the next generation $t+1$ is equal to the best one from generation t .

E. Building Block Functions

We described the energy function for the algorithm with use of a few auxiliary building blocks, defining only expected dependencies within their ground states. Now we finally introduce exact formulas for these building block functions. We introduced five functions: `assert_opposite`, `assert_if_then_else`, `assert_AND`, `check_equality` and `compare_f`, as presented in Table I.

Let us note that each desired dependence could be seen as a set of variables and a set of value assignments that are valid according to that dependence. For example, for `assert_opposite(a, b)` we have 2 variables and 4 value assignments, but only two of them are valid, namely $(a = 1, b = -1)$ and $(a = -1, b = 1)$ because they are opposite values. There exists in the literature a common mechanism that drives the development of exact formulas for given desired features [12]. Namely, we define a quadratic formula that is minimal iff the values assignment is valid. We emphasize that, when a number of configurations is valid, we have to define the formula in such a way that, the energy, *i.e.* the function's value, in every case has to be the same.

First, let us consider the case of two variables taking opposite values. We define a function

$$\text{assert_opposite}(a, b) = ab + 1 \quad (15)$$

that has its optimal value, 0, iff variables a and b have

opposite signs.

Similarly, we introduce a function that implements conditional dependence. In particular, we consider

$$\text{assert_if_then_else}(a, b, c) = (a - 1)c - (a + 1)b + 2 \quad (16)$$

that is designed to obtain minimal value iff relation $(a \implies b \wedge \neg a \implies c)$ is satisfied. For each of possible values of a only one of the terms is non-zero, asserting that the minimal value, 0 is obtained only for the correct values of the rest of the variables.

The third function is the logical AND operation. In particular we consider a function

$$\text{assert_AND}(a, \{b, c\}) = bc - 2ab - 2ac - b - c + 2a + 3 \quad (17)$$

that has its optimal value 0 iff $a = \text{AND}(b, c)$. We will also use the same notation for a collection of variables

$$\text{assert_AND}(a, (b_1, \dots)) \quad (18)$$

that returns a formula that asserts $a = \text{AND}(b_1, \dots)$.

The next function is designed to provide equality check. Given two of the Ising model variables a, b and one auxiliary variable e that does not interact with any other one, we can introduce a function, that will be optimal if and only if variable e encodes a logical value corresponding to the condition $s_1 = s_2$. That is, e is equal to 1 (**true**) if the condition holds and -1 (**false**) otherwise. We can assert that the resulting energy is the same when $a = b$ and $a \neq b$. Such function is denoted as

$$\text{check_equality}(e, (a, b)). \quad (19)$$

FIG. 9. Illustration of the `check_equality` building block.

There are a number of ways to define such a function. In here we propose to introduce 2 auxiliary variables c, d such that $c = 1$ iff $a \leq b$ and $d = 1$ iff $a \geq b$. Thus, the relationship between the pair (a, b) and e will be implemented through these variables as shown in Fig. 9. We will define `check_equality` as a sum of two functions f^{E1} and f^{E2} . The first one is defined as

$$f^{\text{E1}}(a, b, c, d) = (a - b)c + (b - a)d - c - d - ab + 3 \quad (20)$$

and is designed in such a way that variables c and d are assigned valid values in all minimal energy states. To introduce the relationship with variable e we define the second function

$$f^{E2}(c, d, e) = -e(c + d - 1) + 1 \quad (21)$$

As the configuration $(c, d) = (-1, -1)$ would mean that $a > b$ and $a < b$, which is impossible, the optimal energy for the rest of the cases is obtained for the correct value of variable e and is always the same. Finally we obtain

$$\text{check_equality}(e, (a, b)) = f^{E1}(a, b, d, e) + f^{E2}(d, e, c). \quad (22)$$

Finally, we define how a comparison of two individuals is done. Let us recall the comparison condition which has been introduced as

$$c = 1 \iff f(\mathbf{y}) \leq f(\mathbf{x}). \quad (23)$$

We do this by introducing new k -bit integer variable $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, \dots, v_k)$, that store the value of $f(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{y})$. We propose to encode integer v into a bit string in such a way that the most significant bit v_k decides whether $v \geq 0$ or $v < 0$. This will make the dependence between c and the sign of the integer possible.

We introduce the integer by assigning new k -bit string

$$(v_1, \dots, v_k), \quad (24)$$

which will be considered as integer variable \mathbf{v} [12]. The translation can be defined such that the value is equal to

$$\text{value}(\mathbf{v}) = -1/2 + \sum_{i=1}^k 2^{i-2} v_i \in [-2^{k-1}, 2^{k-1} - 1], \quad (25)$$

which allows negative and positive values because $v_i \in \{-1, 1\}$, and satisfies

$$v_k = +1 \iff \text{value}(\mathbf{v}) \geq 0. \quad (26)$$

To assert that $\text{value}(\mathbf{v}) = (f(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{y}))$ is satisfied for all minimal energy states we define

$$\begin{aligned} \text{compare}_f(v_k, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; \mathbf{v}) = \\ (\text{value}(\mathbf{v}) - (f(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{y})))^2, \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

which is a quadratic function if the fitness function f is linear. Now, we can consider $c = v_k$, so that the comparison bit is the same bit as the most significant bit of the fitness difference. The length of the integer variable will depend on the problem size, so that it is possible to represent the maximal allowed value. For $f(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{y})$ in range $[-A, A]$ to be able to represent all of the potential values we chose $k = \lceil \log_2(A + 1) + 1 \rceil$.

Let us note that for a fitness function that is not linear the can use the same approach. The only difference would be the need to reduce the resulting function to a quadratic one, which can be done for any pseudo-boolean function using auxiliary variables [27].

V. PHASE III: COMPLETE EXAMPLE – TUTORIAL

In this section we show how to develop a complete algorithm for a given exemplary optimization problem. The algorithm as introduced in section IV provides what can be seen as a algorithm sheet for developing a wide family of EAs, that only needs to be filled with the fitness function of the specific problem.

Thus, we explicitly define the fitness function that we use in the example. **Then, we make it work with the translation algorithm by explicitly defining comparison function, which was given in Eq. (27) in a generic way.**

A. ONEMAX Problem

For all of the simulations and experiments to come in this paper we will use one fitness function. For this purpose we choose ONEMAX optimization problem. This basic problem is a standard one in theoretical studies of optimization methods, especially when the focus is in the algorithm. We consider an optimization task, which is to find a solution with the maximal number of ones in it. Let us remind that the solution variables are equal to ± 1 and the value of the function is in the range $[-n, n]$. The considered fitness function assigns to every tentative solution $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathcal{S}$ a value of

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = -\sum_{i=1}^n x_i. \quad (28)$$

Let us note that in the ONEMAX problem the variables usually take 0/1 values. We define the problem with values from $\{-1, +1\}$, which also makes $f(\mathbf{x})$ take only even (odd) values for even (odd) size n . This does not change the properties of the problem significantly and makes it easier to implement in the Ising model.

B. Comparison of Two Individuals in the Quantum Device – ONEMAX Case

Let us recall that in Eq. (27) we defined the comparison function as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{compare}_f(v_k, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}; \mathbf{v}) = \\ (\text{value}(\mathbf{v}) - (f(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{y})))^2 \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

That is the only part of the translation algorithm that needs to be adapted to the fitness function. In this example we want $c^{(t)}$ to be +1 if $(\sum x_i^{(t)} - x_i'^{(t)}) \geq 0$ and -1 otherwise.

To assert that equality $\text{value}(\mathbf{v}^{(t)}) = (\sum_i x_i^{(t)} - x_i'^{(t)})$

holds for all minimal energy states we define

$$\text{compare}_{\text{ONEMAX}}(c^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}'^{(t)}, \mathbf{v}^{(t)}) = \quad (30)$$

$$\left(\text{value}(\mathbf{v}^{(t)}) - \sum_i (x_i^{(t)} - x_i'^{(t)}) \right)^2$$

which is a quadratic function. We can consider $c^{(t)} = v_k^{(t)}$, so that the comparison variable is the same as the variable corresponding to the most significant bit of the variable v . The number of bits of the variable v will depend on the problem size, so that it is possible to represent the maximal possible value. In this case we want to store the value $\sum (x_i^{(t)} - x_i'^{(t)})$ which is in range $[-2n, +2n]$. Thus, to be able to represent all of the potential values we chose $k = \lceil \log_2(2n + 1) + 1 \rceil$.

VI. PHASE IV: RUNNING EAS ON AN ACTUAL QUANTUM DEVICE (DWAVE)

There are many ways to solve an Ising model problem, once the energy function is defined. If we had access to a machine with no limit on the size of the system, we could run the algorithm as one Ising model problem. Unfortunately that is not feasible with state-of-the-art devices.

In this section we show how to adapt the algorithm to solve an example problem with an actual device. We present the results we have obtained and discuss the limitations of the current devices.

A. Quantum EA Execution

In this paper we aim at using a quantum annealing device to run the quantum EA(1+1) algorithm. The device that we are using can handle up to 2048 binary variables with interactions fitting the device's internal architecture or 64 fully connected binary variables (see sec III B). This makes solving the annealing problem in a single run of the device unfeasible. Even for ONEMAX problem and size $n = 10$ that we use in the experiments, the total number of variables exceeds 64.

This issue is inevitable when tackling any non-trivial problem. A common way to solve it is a kind of a divide and conquer idea, solving the problem in parts [28, 29]: iteratively choose a subset of variables that will be optimized, fixing the values of the others.

The whole algorithm energy function for one generation has been defined as a sum of energy function components. Let us write this again, with a generation number superscript

$$F^{(t)} = F_M^{(t)} + F_E^{(t)} + F_R^{(t)}, \quad (31)$$

where

$$F_M^{(t)} = \sum_i f_M(m_i^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}),$$

$$F_E^{(t)} = f_E(c^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}^{(t)}, \mathbf{x}'^{(t)}), \quad (32)$$

$$F_R^{(t)} = \sum_i f_R(c^{(t)}, x_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)}, x_i^{(t+1)}).$$

Using this representation one can notice that each function acts on a limited number of variables. We use this fact, and run the quantum annealing for these components separately.

Thus, we propose a sequence of steps. During the computation we store the set of already fixed variables V , starting with $V = \emptyset$. For each run of the quantum annealing device we

- select an energy function component E and the variables W included in E that are not in V ,
- define energy function $D(W) = E(W \cup V)$, that depends only on the variables W , substituting the variables in V with already obtained values,
- run the annealing device, using energy function D as the input, obtaining values for variables in W ,
- store the values of the variables in W , and update $V = V \cup W$.

The resulting procedure is as follows:

1. Start with an empty set of already fixed variables $V = \emptyset$.
2. For the first generation $t = 1$ we use energy function $F = 0$ and $W = \{x_1^{(1)}, \dots, x_n^{(1)}\}$, in order to obtain constraints free initial sampling.
3. Consider $F = F_M^{(t)}$ energy function and variables $W = \{m_i^{(t)}, x_i'^{(t)} : i = 1 \dots, n\}$ as the input to the annealing device.
4. Consider $F = F_E^{(t)}$ energy function and variables $W = \{c^{(t)}\} \cup \{w_i^{(t)} : i = 1 \dots, k\}$ as the input to the annealing device.
5. Consider $F = F_R^{(t)}$ energy function and variables $W = \{x_i^{(t+1)} : i = 1 \dots, n\}$ as the input to the annealing device.
6. Go back to step 2 for each new generation, with $t = t + 1$, until $t = T$.

In this case we consider at most n variables in a single run of the annealing device.

FIG. 10. Fitness function value evolution in time (for selected successful runs of the quantum EA algorithm).

B. Experimental Results

As an example we consider the ONEMAX problem for solution size of $n = 10$. The quantum EA is still a non-deterministic algorithm and thus we also need to make a statistical analysis of its results over independent runs. The non-deterministic behavior gives no warranty of reaching the optimal solution and thus we decided to bound the maximum number of mutations per independent run to 100. We aimed at more than 30 *successful runs*, *i.e.* runs that reach the optimal solution. This resulted in 49 independent runs of the algorithm. There are also two main parameters of the device we need to set before any experiment: the annealing time, and the number of repetitions as explained in Section III B. The device has been set to perform the annealing procedure in 0.02 ms and perform 100 repetitions. The parameters of the experiment are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II. The parameters of the experiment.

Experiment parameter	Value
Problem size n	10
Maximum number of mutations per run	100
Number of independent runs	49
Annealing time	0.02 ms
Number of annealing repetitions	100

As a result, we found that 31 (63.3%) out of 49 runs reached the optimal solution in less than 100 mutations

FIG. 11. Box plot of the fitness function value evolution in time (for successful runs of the quantum EA algorithm).

(with the minimum being 13 and the maximum being 88). All of the successful runs are shown in Fig. 11. For the statistical analysis we focus on two figures of merit. First, we consider the number of mutations that is needed to reach the optimal solution (*mutations to solution*) within the successful runs. Secondly, we study the area under the curve showing how the value of the fitness function changes with successive mutations (see Fig. 11). We put the mean values and standard deviations in Table III. The histogram of the distribution of the number of mutations to solution is presented in Fig. 13. For comparison purposes we run the canonical EA(1+1) on the same problem with the same algorithm's parameters. **The two obtained distributions are very similar. Thus, in the considered case the quantum EA indeed provided a reliable implementation of the canonical EA in a quantum device.**

TABLE III. Canonical EA and quantum EA convergence results (average values for the successful runs).

Algorithm	Mutations to solution	Area under the curve
Classic	41.65 ± 20.98	911.81 ± 43.73
Quantum	47.00 ± 20.50	829.68 ± 81.36

Within the 49 independent runs we computed a total of 3257 mutations/generations (summing up all the generations of all the independent runs). Out of them, 332 (10.2%) were repeated due to errors: the returned solution was not the correct ground state, which resulted

FIG. 12. Final fitness histogram for all of the runs of the quantum EA algorithm. In the experiment the fitness function could only take even integer value.

FIG. 13. Mutations to solution histogram for the successful runs of the quantum EA algorithm.

in incorrect relations between variables, as discussed in section III B. Designing an energy function that would be more robust to the quantum device’s imperfections errors could be an interesting goal for future work.

The results regarding the usage time of the quantum computing unit are presented in Table IV. **The time it took to do a complete device call for all of the computation we have done exhibited very little variance. However, it contains some inevitable delays caused by network, device’s tasks queuing system etc., thus we might expect some variations in it when repeated.**

TABLE IV. Duration of particular phases of computation with the quantum computing unit.

QPU task	Duration
Annealing time (one repetition)	0.02 ms
One repetition t_{rep}	0.16 ms
QPU Initialization t_{init} (avg.)	7.78 ms
Total QPU time t_{QPU} (avg.)	23.28 ms
Complete call t_q (avg.)	747.37 ms

VII. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE WORK

The main goal of this paper has been to provide a complete guide to implementing an evolutionary algorithm with a quantum annealing device. We started with a canonical EA(1+1) and introduced a few steps that ended with a quantum EA algorithm.

We introduced slightly modified the standard EA description to fit quantum programming. In this new description operations of the EA are actual relations between variables. For this purpose we also added new variables to make the translation to the quantum algorithm easier.

Then we translated these relations into an energy function F minimized via a quantum annealing procedure. The development of the energy function has been split into the components that we introduced separately, explaining their implementation on a quantum device in detail. This translation, annealing, reverse translation steps compose the quantum EA.

The end effect of both canonical and quantum EA is the same. The resulting algorithm is also a metaheuristic, or an algorithm sheet, that needs to be adapted to a given problem. We provided an example considering the ONEMAX problem.

Finally, we used an actual device to run the example. We report the resulting convergence statistics, error rates and running times. The basic statistics are compared with the canonical algorithm.

The results obtained by running the quantum

EA on an actual device are very close to the results of the classical EA. The average number of mutations till finding a solution of the problem was 47.00 and 41.65 correspondingly. Thus, on average, it took 12.85% more mutations to reach the optimal solution with the quantum EA. However, the difference is small considering the standard deviations of the obtained results.

The algorithm is not free of errors. The current design resulted in a 10% error rate, defined as the share of all of the computed mutations that had to be repeated.

We see two main directions for future work. First, we could look into the details of the implementation. The proposed implementation of the relations did not save us from errors. Designing an energy function that would

more robust to the quantum device's imperfections could be an interesting goal for future work. Second, we could look into a more general picture: the simple recreation of an EA is a limited first step.. Now, having a starting point we would like to try to modify the algorithm in such a way that it is no longer equivalent, searching for a way to harness the quantum resources.

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Appendix A: Implementation Example

D-Wave Systems Inc. provides a number of tools for developing and running annealing procedures. Many of them are freely available, e.g. at github [30]. For simulation one can use *e.g.* `dwave-qbsolv`¹ or `dimod`² and for communication with actual device `dwave-cloud-client`³ tools.

The most popular way to define and solve Ising problems with these tools is to build a python script with the energy function represented as a pair of python dictionaries, *i.e.* `dict` objects. Namely, as the energy function as defined in Eq. (2) is represented by factors h_i and $J_{i,j}$, one needs to simply build objects that map i to h_i and a pair (i, j) to $J_{i,j}$.

We will proceed with a basic example, that provides a complete working code for a simple energy function, and then sketch the implementation of the whole quantum EA.

1. Basic Example

Let us give an example. In section IV E in Eq. (15) we introduced an `assert_opposite` function. Let us recall that

$$\text{assert_opposite}(a, b) = ab + 1$$

As stated in Section IV we begin with establishing a mapping between variables and Ising model sites. We assume that $a = s_0$ and $b = s_1$. Thus, if we want to represent this energy function in the form introduced in Eq. (2) we obtain $s = (s_0, s_1)$, $h_0 = 0$, $h_1 = 0$, $J_{0,1} = 1$. We omit the constant factor $+1$, because it does not affect which of the states are the ground states.

The implementation of the problem above could look like this:

```
site_a = 0
site_b = 1

linear_terms = {site_a: 0, site_b: 0}
quadratic_terms = {(site_a, site_b): 1}

import dimod
solver = dimod.ExactSolver()

sample = solver.sample_ising(
    linear_terms, quadratic_terms).first
print(sample)
```

¹ <https://github.com/dwavesystems/qbsolv>

² <https://github.com/dwavesystems/dimod>

³ <https://github.com/dwavesystems/dwave-cloud-client>

First we establish a mapping between variables a and b and the Ising model sites, which we represent as integers 0 and 1. Then we implement the mapping for the linear terms $i \mapsto h_i$ as a `dict` object `linear_terms`, and repeat the same for quadratic terms. We use the `dimod` tool provided by D-Wave Systems (this tool provides a method `sample_ising` that can be used to substitute the annealing device).

The resulting object maps Ising model sites to values in $\{-1, +1\}$. We expect to obtain opposite values at the sites corresponding to a and b . One of the possible outputs look like this:

```
Sample(sample={0: 1, 1: -1}, energy=-1.0,
        num_occurrences=1)
```

In this example we used a classical simulation of the quantum device (in the paper we always use a real quantum device). Using the actual device to obtain the samples would only require changing the `solver` object to be an instance of a different class, which would however implement the same interface.

2. Implementation of the Algorithm

Running the algorithm described in the paper can be done in the same way as the previous example. It requires properly preparing the mapping between the Ising model sites and the algorithm variables, and then translating the formulas into `dict` objects.

Let us assume we have implemented the building block function from Section IV E.

- `assert_opposite(linear_terms, quadratic_terms, site_a, site_b)`,
- `assert_if_then_else(linear_terms, quadratic_terms, site_a, site_b, site_c)`,
- `assert_AND(linear_terms, quadratic_terms, site_a, site_list_b)`,
- `check_equality(linear_terms, quadratic_terms, site_a, site_b, site_e)`,
- `compare(linear_terms, quadratic_terms, site_x, site_y, site_c)`.

that given `dict` objects `linear_terms`, `quadratic_terms` and some Ising model sites, update the objects to include the corresponding building block function. For example, as shown in the previous example

```
def assert_opposite(linear_terms,
                    quadratic_terms,
                    site_a, site_b):
    quadratic_terms[(site_a,
                     site_b)] += 1
```

could be an implementation of the `assert_opposite` function.

Then building the energy function for the algorithm could look like

```

lt = linear_terms
qt = quadratic_terms

for t in generations:
    %mutation
    for i in solution_variables:
        assert_AND(lt , qt ,
            mutation_auxiliary[t][i],
            mutation_control[t][i])
        check_equality(lt ,qt ,
            original_individual[t][i],
            mutated_individual[t][i],
            mutation_equality_check[t][i])
        assert_opposite(lt , qt ,
            mutation_control[t][i],
            mutation_equality_check[t][i])
    %comparison
    compare(lt , qt ,
        original_individual[t][i],

```

```

        mutated_individual[t][i],
        comparison[t])
    %replacement
    for i in solution_variables:
        check_equality(lt ,qt ,
            original_individual[t][i],
            selected_individual[t][i],
            selected_original_equality[t][i])
        check_equality(lt ,qt ,
            mutated_individual[t][i],
            selected_individual[t][i],
            selected_mutated_equality[t][i])
        assert_if_then_else(lt , qt ,
            comparison_result[t],
            selected_original_equality[t][i],
            selected_mutated_equality[t][i])
    sample = solver.sample_ising(lt , qt
        ).first[0]
    for i in solution_variables
        print(
            sample[selected_individual[T-1][i]])

```

where the names refer to the algorithm model variables as described in Section II B.